

ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Entrepreneurship can be defined as the process of identifying, developing, and bringing a new idea, product, or service to market, often by taking financial and personal risks. Entrepreneurs play a crucial role in driving economic growth, innovation, and job creation.

Most entrepreneurs are innovative, risk takers, adaptable and engage in value creation activities. The roles of entrepreneurs are essential as they help to foster economic growth, create jobs, thereby, reducing unemployment, and bring groundbreaking technologies and ideas to the market.

Entrepreneurship is a solution to unemployment as entrepreneurs will open doors to a new business, ventures or alliances. It makes people self-reliant for their means of livelihood and feeding. When unemployment is high and the economy is contracting or stagnating, dynamic entrepreneurship could help turn the economy around.

There are a few challenges faced by existing and upcoming entrepreneurs including access to capital, regulatory barriers, unstable exchange rate, increase energy cost, high interest rate, increasing cost of production, infrastructural deficits etc. These challenges could make potential entrepreneurs to reduce production time and result in loss of jobs, uncompetitiveness in the foreign market and close of some businesses.

Some types of entrepreneurs

- i. **Innovative entrepreneurs:** These types of entrepreneurs are found in developed countries. They are the ones who introduce a new type of good, a new method of production and discover ways for it to get to the market. He is a good leader and takes up opportunities to introduce new techniques in the market. They can only work within a certain level of development and people look forward to change and improvement. An innovative entrepreneur is scarce to be found in an underdeveloped country and they play important roles. An example of an Innovative entrepreneur is Elon Musk, the inventor of electric cars.
- ii. **Adoptive entrepreneurs:** These types of entrepreneurs can also be called imitative entrepreneurs. These types of entrepreneurs tend to imitate or copy innovative or initiated ideas. They are ready to adopt successful innovations that have already been made. They imitate, skills, technologies, ideas, and prefer to imitate rather than make their own. An example of this type of entrepreneur is Walton BD. He has introduced motorbikes, refrigerators and other electronic appliances not being the original inventor of those products.
- iii. **Drone Entrepreneurs:** These entrepreneurs are known for not adopting and using opportunities to change. They are constant in what they do as they prefer their old methods even if they suffer losses. They always prefer the traditional way and not the modern way and these could make them lose out of the market and make their products uneconomical. They do not want to be involved in technological advancements.
- iv. **Fabian Entrepreneurs:** These types of entrepreneurs are filled with doubt and are very skeptical. They do not want to introduce any change, take risks nor adopt any that has been made. They are usually shy, lazy and are determined by custom, tradition, etc. They will only imitate when they are very sure that there would be no loss in the enterprise.

- v. **Lifestyle Entrepreneurs:** Lifestyle entrepreneurs are the types that yearn to make profit with their passion, examples are, a baker who is passionate about baking, the baker loves what they are doing and is also earning from this means. Another example is a saxophonist, someone who loves music and plays at events. The saxophonist does what he loves and also earn from it. These types of entrepreneurs place their passion before profits as they are combining passion interest and profit making. They go into this and make sure it is for long term sustainability, he may choose to work alone and keep it under his control or employ people and they always invest heavily on this business. If the business survives, the entrepreneur takes risk but is independent.

It is important to note that entrepreneurship is vital for fostering innovation, addressing societal challenges, and ensuring long-term economic sustainability. It thrives in environments that encourage creativity, collaboration, and risk-taking. Therefore government should encourage entrepreneurs especially in the non-oil sector by encouraging and subsidizing entrepreneurs to participate in trade fairs, provide incentives such as tax reduction, give access to credit with low interest payback rates and create awareness on trade agreements that could be beneficial to entrepreneurs.